

Clinician Data Collection Checklist for Gestational Hypertension (NICE NG133)

- This checklist is completed by clinicians based on patient medical records.
- Each item is scored for compliance with NICE NG133 standards.
- Responses should be marked as Yes (Y), No (N), or Not Applicable (N/A) where appropriate.

Patient Information

- Case ID:
- Age:
- Gravida / Para:
- GA at Diagnosis:
- Source (Clinic / Ward):
- Date of diagnosis:
- Date of delivery / discharge:
- Audit period: Cases diagnosed between ___ / ___ / ____ and ___ / ___ / ____

Diagnosis Criteria (Y/N)

1. BP \geq 140/90 after 20 weeks confirmed on two readings	
▪ First BP reading	
▪ Second BP reading	
2. No proteinuria at diagnosis (dipstick <1+ or negative):	

Blood Pressure Monitoring (Y/ N / N/A)

3. BP monitored once or twice weekly as per NICE: Yes (..) OR No (..) OR N/A(..)

Proteinuria Monitoring (Y/ N / N/A)

4. Dipstick testing done once or twice weekly: Yes (..) OR No (..) OR N/A(..)

Laboratory Monitoring (Y/N)

- 5. Full blood count, LFT, RFT done at diagnosis: Yes (..) OR No (..)
- 6. Weekly labs performed – Yes (..) OR No (..) OR N/A(..)

Fetal Monitoring (Y/N)

- 7. Ultrasound at diagnosis: Yes (..) OR No (..)
- 8. Growth scan repeated every 2–4 weeks – Yes (..) OR No (..) OR N/A(..)

CTG Monitoring (Y/N)

- 9. CTG performed only if clinically indicated: Yes (..) OR No (..) OR N/A(..)

Antihypertensive Management (Y/N)

- 10. Antihypertensive treatment given when BP persistently >140/90 mmHg: Yes (..) OR No (..) OR N/A(..)
- 11. First-line drug used (Labetalol unless contraindicated): Yes (..) OR No (..) OR N/A(..)
 - If labetalol is contraindicated (reason documented): Yes (..) OR No (..) OR N/A(..)
- 12. BP target achieved \leq 135/85 mmHg: Yes (..) OR No (..) OR N/A(..)

Admission Criteria (Y/N)

- 13. Severe HTN \geq 160/110 admitted appropriately: Yes (..) OR No (..)

Timing of Birth (Y/N)

- 14. Timing of birth appropriate as per NICE NG133 – Yes (..) OR No (..)

GA at Delivery	
Early Delivery <37w with Medical Indication?	

Scoring System

- Each compliant item = 1 point.
- Maximum score = 14 points.

Interpretation:

- $\geq 80\%$ → Fully compliant with NICE NG133
- 60-79% → Partially compliant; improvement required
- $< 60\%$ → Poor compliance; urgent action needed